

ON SOLUTIONS TO ERDŐS' LAST EQUATION

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Received: 2/4/21, Revised: 6/21/21, Accepted: 11/25/21, Published: 12/3/21

Abstract

We focus on the solutions to Erdős's last equation $n(x_1 + \cdots + x_n) = x_1 \cdots x_n$. Shiu classified the solutions into the classes $C_\ell(n)$, where $\ell+1$ is the number of $x_i > 1$ and presented some sufficient conditions for $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$. In this paper, we consider the set $C_3(n)$, which implies that we deal with the solutions to $n(n-4+a+b+c+d) = abcd$ with $a, b, c, d > 1$. We introduce a new method and prove that $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ if $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{180180}$ and $n \geq 6$. Furthermore, we prove that $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ for any $6 \leq n \leq 10^{24}$.

1. Introduction

The equal-sum-and-product problem is known as finding the integer solutions to the Diophantine equation $x_1 + \cdots + x_n = x_1 \cdots x_n$. Considerable theoretical and computational research has been conducted for this problem [1, 2, 4, 5]. By contrast, some research has also been performed on the solutions of a similar equation:

$$n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = \prod_{i=1}^n x_i, \quad (1)$$

where $n > 1$ and x_i are positive integers satisfying $x_1 \leq x_2 \leq \cdots \leq x_n$. As Erdős asked Richard Guy [3, Problem D24] if he knew anything about Equation (1), this equation is called Erdős's last equation (ELE_n).

We make several observations as the first step towards solving Equation (1). When $n = 2$, we can simply conclude that the only solutions (x_1, x_2) with $x_1 \leq x_2$ to the equation $2(x_1 + x_2) = x_1 x_2$ are $(x_1, x_2) = (3, 6), (4, 4)$. Therefore, we assume $n \geq 3$ throughout this paper. In 2019, Shiu classified the solutions to ELE_n into sets as follows:

$$C_\ell(n) = \{(x_1, \dots, x_n) \mid x_1 = \cdots = x_{n-\ell-1} = 1, 2 \leq x_{n-\ell} \leq \cdots \leq x_n\}.$$

Furthermore, he characterized the set $C_1(n)$ as

$$C_1(n) = \{(\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{n-2}, n+a, n+b) \mid ab = 2n(n-1), 1 \leq a \leq b\}.$$

As $(\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{n-3}, 2, n, 2n - 1), (\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{n-3}, 3, n, n) \in C_2(n)$, we find that the set $C_2(n)$ is not empty for $n \geq 3$. By contrast, for $\ell \geq 3$, it is difficult to establish a deceptively simple result. Thus, for $\ell \geq 3$, Shiu introduced the following two conjectures.

Conjecture 1 (Conjecture $\mathcal{C}_\ell$ of [6]). Let ℓ be a positive integer with $\ell \geq 3$. There exists $n_0(\ell)$ such that $C_\ell(n) \neq \emptyset$ for $n \geq n_0(\ell)$.

Conjecture 2 (Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ of [6]). For $n \geq 6$, integers k and $a, b, c > 1$ exist such that

$$n(n - 4 + a + b + c) \equiv 0 \pmod k, \quad n + k = abc, \quad 1 \leq k \leq n^2. \tag{2}$$

If Conjecture 2 for n is true, then $(1, \dots, 1, a, b, c, d) \in C_3(n)$ with $d = nS/k, S = n - 4 + a + b + c$, and so $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$. Let $\Omega(n)$ be the number of prime divisors of n counted with multiplicity. Shiu indicated that if $\Omega(n + 1) \geq 3$ or n is composite, Conjecture 2 is true. For the former case, we can take $k = 1$ and $n + 1 = abc$. Moreover, for the latter we take $k = n = bc$ and $a = 2$. As a generalization, Shiu proved the following result.

Theorem 1 (Shiu 2019 [6]). *Let $n \geq 6$. If n is composite, or if $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$, then $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$. Moreover, $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ for $6 \leq n \leq 1260001$.*

In this paper, we extend Shiu’s result for $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ as follows.

Theorem 2. *Let $n \geq 6$. Then, $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ if n satisfies at least one of the following three conditions:*

- (i) n is composite, (ii) $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{180180}$, (iii) $6 \leq n \leq 10^{24}$.

The condition (iii) is checked via a computer search using Maxima. Moreover, we present at least one solution $(1, \dots, 1, x_{n-3}, x_{n-2}, x_{n-1}, x_n) \in C_3(n)$ explicitly for each $6 \leq n \leq 10^{24}$. To accomplish this, we create a table (see Appendix) to deal with primes $p \equiv 1 \pmod{180180}$. The table shows a list of sufficient conditions for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$ (together with the explicit solutions), which serve as a filter to sort for sorting out cases where $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$, leaving only a handful of primes less than 10^{24} that must be dealt with directly (see Section 4).

2. Criteria Using the Omega Function

In this section, we show some lemmas that ensure $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ using the Omega function Ω . As Shiu showed that if $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$ or n is composite then $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$, it suffices to consider the case that n is a prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$.

Lemma 1. *Let p be a prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. If $\max\{\Omega(p+1), \Omega(p+2), \Omega(p+4)\} \geq 3$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. When $\Omega(p+1) \geq 3$, Shiu demonstrated this statement [6]. Therefore, it suffices to show the case $\Omega(p+2) \geq 3$ or $\Omega(p+4) \geq 3$. First, we assume $\Omega(p+2) \geq 3$. Then there exists a triple of integers $(s, t, u) \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 2}^3$ such that $p+2 = stu$. As $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$, p is an odd prime and $p+2, s, t$ and u are also odd integers. Therefore, $(n, a, b, c, k) = (p, s, t, u, 2)$ satisfies Congruence (2), and Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for p with $\Omega(p+2) \geq 3$.

Next, we prove that if $\Omega(p+4) \geq 3$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$. As aforementioned, there exists a triple of odd integers $(s, t, u) \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 3}^3$ such that $p+4 = stu$. As $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, one can check that $p-4 + s + t + u \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, and Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for p with $\Omega(p+4) \geq 3$, independent of the choice (s, t, u) .

As Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ implies $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$, this lemma holds. □

Next, we consider $\Omega(p+i)$ for $i \in \{5, 6\}$. Let p be a prime with $\Omega(p+5) = 3$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. Then we find $p+5 = 2 \cdot 3 \cdot q$ with a prime $q \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$. As $p-4 + 2 + 3 + q \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$, there exists no 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 5)$ satisfying Congruence (2). Furthermore, if p be a prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$ and $p+6 = 7 \cdot q \cdot r$ with primes $q \equiv r \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$, then $p-4 + 7 + q + r \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$. Therefore, there exists no 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 6)$ satisfying Congruence (2). By contrast, the following lemma holds.

Lemma 2. *Let p be an odd prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. If $\max\{\Omega(p+5), \Omega(p+6)\} \geq 4$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. First, we assume $\Omega(p+5) \geq 4$. Then there exists a pair of integers $(s, t) \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 2}^2$ such that $p+5 = 6st$. As $p \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, $(s \pmod{5}, t \pmod{5}) \in \{(1, 1), (2, 3), (4, 4)\}$. (If necessary, we swap the role of s and t .) We can choose a 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 5)$ satisfying Congruence (2) as follows:

$$(a, b, c) = \begin{cases} (6, s, t) & \text{if } (s, t) = (1, 1), \\ (2, s, 3t) & \text{if } (s, t) = (2, 3), (4, 4). \end{cases}$$

Therefore, Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for any prime p with $\Omega(p+5) \geq 4$.

Next, we prove that if $\Omega(p+6) \geq 4$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$. As above, there exists a triple of odd integers $(s, t, u) \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 3}^3$ such that $p+6 = 7stu$. As $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, it follows that $(s \pmod{6}, t \pmod{6}, u \pmod{6}) \in \{(1, 1, 1), (1, 5, 5)\}$ (if necessary, we swap the role of s, t and u). Then the 5-tuple $(p, 7, s, tu, 6)$ satisfies Congruence (2). Therefore, Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for any prime p with $\Omega(p+6) \geq 4$.

This proves the lemma. □

Next, we deal with $\Omega(p+3)$. If $\Omega(p+3) = 4$ and $p+3 = 4qr$ with $q \equiv r \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, following which, $p-4+a+b+c \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ for any triple (a, b, c) with $abc =$

$4qr$. Hence, there is no 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 3)$ satisfying Congruence (2). Similarly, if $\Omega(p + 9) = 4$ and $p + 9 = 10qr$ with $q \equiv r \equiv 2 \pmod 3$, then there is no 5-tuple satisfying Congruence (2).

Lemma 3. *Let p be an odd prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. If $\max\{\Omega(p + 3), \Omega(p + 9)\} \geq 5$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. First, we assume $\Omega(p + 3) \geq 5$. Then there exists a triple of integers $(s, t, u) \in \mathbf{Z}_{>2}^3$ such that $p + 2 = 4stu$. As $p \equiv 1 \pmod 3$, $(s \pmod 3, t \pmod 3, u \pmod 3) \in \{(1, 1, 1), (2, 2, 1)\}$ (if necessary, we swap the role of s, t and u). Then the 5-tuple $(p, 4, st, u, 3)$ satisfies Congruence (2). Therefore, Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for any prime p with $\Omega(p + 3) \geq 5$.

Additionally, if $\Omega(p + 9) \geq 5$ then $p + 9 = 10stu$. As $p \equiv 1 \pmod 3$, $(s \pmod 3, t \pmod 3, u \pmod 3) \in \{(1, 1, 1), (2, 2, 1)\}$ (if necessary, we swap the role of s, t and u). Then the 5-tuple $(p, 10, st, u, 9)$ satisfies Congruence (2). Therefore, Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for any prime p with $\Omega(p + 9) \geq 5$.

This proves the lemma. □

Next, we compute a lower bound on $\Omega(p + 7)$. If $\Omega(p + 7) = 6$ and $p + 7 = 4q_1q_2q_3q_4$ with $q_i \equiv 2 \pmod 7$, then it holds that $p - 4 + a + b + c \not\equiv 0 \pmod 7$ for any triple (a, b, c) with $abc = 4q_1q_2q_3q_4$. Hence, there is no 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 7)$ satisfying Congruence (2). By contrast, we can prove the following lemma.

Lemma 4. *Let p be an odd prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. If $\Omega(p + 7) \geq 7$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. If $\Omega(p + 7) \geq 7$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$, then we can factor $p + 7 = 4q_1q_2q_3q_4q_5$. One can check that when order is irrelevant, there are 42 possible quintuples $(r_1, \dots, r_5) \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}^5$ with $q_i \equiv r_i \pmod 7$. Then we can choose a pair $(p, a, b, c, 7)$ satisfying Congruence (2) as follows:

$$(a, b, c) = \begin{cases} (q_i, q_j, \frac{p+7}{q_iq_j}) & \text{if } (r_i, r_j) \in \{(1, 1), (3, 3), (3, 4)\}, \\ (2q_i, 2q_j, \frac{p+7}{4q_iq_j}) & \text{if } (r_i, r_j) \in \{(2, 5), (3, 4), (4, 4), (5, 5)\}, \\ (q_i, 4q_j, \frac{p+7}{4q_iq_j}) & \text{if } r_i = 1, r_j = 2, \\ (4q_i, q_jq_k, \frac{p+7}{4q_iq_jq_k}) & \text{if } r_i = 2, r_j = r_k = 6, \\ (q_i, q_jq_k, \frac{p+7}{q_iq_jq_k}) & \text{if } r_i = 1, r_j = r_k = 6. \end{cases}$$

As any quintuple satisfies one of the above five conditions, the proof is complete. □

We can also compute the sufficient condition of $\Omega(p + i)$ for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$ for a larger integer i . For example, we can obtain lower bounds on $\Omega(p + 14)$ and $\Omega(p + 20)$ as follows.

Lemma 5. *Let p be an odd prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. Then the following hold.*

1. If $\Omega(p + 14) \geq 5$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.
2. If $\Omega(p + 20) \geq 4$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. First, we assume $\Omega(p + 14) \geq 5$. Then we can factor $p + 14 = 15stu$. Without loss of generality, we can assume $s \equiv 1, 3, 9, 11 \pmod{14}$ (if necessary, we swap the role of s, t and u). We can choose a 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 14)$ satisfying Congruence (2) as follows:

$$(a, b, c) = \begin{cases} (15, s, tu) & \text{if } s \equiv 1 \pmod{14}, \\ (3, s, 5tu) & \text{if } s \equiv 3, 11 \pmod{14}, \\ (3, 5s, tu) & \text{if } s \equiv 9 \pmod{14}. \end{cases}$$

Next, we prove the second assertion. If $\Omega(p + 20) \geq 4$, we can factor $p + 20 = 21st$. Without loss of generality, we can assume $s \equiv 1, 7, 9, 11, 17, 19 \pmod{20}$ (if necessary, we swap the role of s and t). Then, we can choose a 5-tuple $(p, a, b, c, 20)$ satisfying Congruence (2) as follows:

$$(a, b, c) = \begin{cases} (21, s, t) & \text{if } s \equiv 1, 11 \pmod{20}, \\ (7, s, 3t) & \text{if } s \equiv 7, 9, 17, 19 \pmod{20}. \end{cases}$$

Based on the above argument, the proof is complete. □

Furthermore, when k is not a divisor of 1260, it does not necessarily follow that $p \equiv 1 \pmod{k}$, and the computation of lower bound on $\Omega(p + k)$ may be slightly complicated. The least positive integer that is not a divisor of 1260 is 8. To conclude this section, we prove the following lemma about the lower bound on $\Omega(p + 8)$.

Lemma 6. *Let p be an odd prime with $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. If $\Omega(p + 8) \geq 5$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. Assuming $\Omega(p + 8) \geq 5$, there exists a triple (s, t, u) with $p + 8 = 9stu$. Without loss of generality, we can assume $s \equiv 1, 5 \pmod{8}$ (if necessary, we swap the role of s, t and u). We can check the 5-tuple $(p, 9, s, tu, 8)$ satisfying Congruence (2), independent of the remainder of p divided by 8.

Therefore, we have proven the lemma. □

3. Criteria on Modulus

In this section, we consider $C_3(p)$ for a prime $p \geq 7$. First, we show the following lemma to introduce a way different from Shiu's way.

Lemma 7. *Let p be a prime number. If $(x_1, \dots, x_p) \in C_3(p)$, then $p|x_p$.*

Proof. Let $(x_1, \dots, x_p) \in C_3(p)$. If we assume $x_{p-1} \geq p$, then we have

$$x_{p-3} = \frac{p(\sum_{i=1}^{p-4} x_i + x_{p-2} + x_{p-1} + x_p)}{\prod_{i=1}^{p-4} x_i x_{p-2} x_{p-1} x_p - p} \leq \frac{p(p-4+2+p+p)}{2p^2-p} \leq \frac{3}{2}.$$

This contradicts $(x_1, \dots, x_p) \in C_3(p)$, and it follows that $x_{p-1} < p$.

As it holds that

$$p \sum_{i=1}^p x_i = \prod_{i=1}^p x_i,$$

p divides $\prod_{i=1}^p x_i$. Combining this with $x_{p-1} < p$, it is proven that $p|x_p$. □

Lemma 7 ensures that we can denote $x_p = kp$ with $k \geq 1$. In this case, Erdős’s last equation becomes

$$p(p-4+x_{p-3}+x_{p-2}+x_{p-1}+kp) = x_{p-3}x_{p-2}x_{p-1}kp,$$

that is,

$$x_{p-3} = \frac{p-4+x_{p-2}+x_{p-1}+kp}{x_{p-2}x_{p-1}k-1},$$

where $k \geq 1$ and $2 \leq x_i < p$ for $i \in \{p-3, p-2, p-1\}$. For simplicity, we forget the condition $x_{p-3} \leq x_{p-2} \leq x_{p-1}$. Therefore, we only need to find a triple of positive integers $(a, b) \in \mathbf{Z}_{\geq 2}^2, c \geq 1$ such that the congruence

$$p-4+a+b+cp \equiv 0 \pmod{abc-1} \tag{3}$$

holds. We analyze whether $C_3(p)$ is empty for all primes in an arithmetic progression using the method of Shiu’s paper. First, we prove the following theorem.

Theorem 3. *For any prime $p \not\equiv 1 \pmod{11}$, it holds that $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. It suffices to show the case $p \equiv 1 \pmod{1260}$. If $p \equiv 2 \pmod{11}$, then we can express $p = 13860m + 2521$. Assuming $k = 20$ in Congruence (2), we find $p+20 = 231(60m+11) = 3 \cdot 7 \cdot 11 \cdot (60m+11)$ and $p-4+11+21+(60m+11) \equiv 0 \pmod{20}$. Therefore, $(n, a, b, c, k) = (13860m + 2521, 11, 21, 60m + 11, 20)$ satisfies Congruence (2), and Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ holds for $p \equiv 2 \pmod{11}$. Next, we find triples (a, b, c) satisfying Congruence (3). By direct computation, we find the following table:

$p \pmod{11}$	(a, b, c)	$p \pmod{11}$	(a, b, c)
3	(10, 10, 1)	7	(3, 2, 2)
4	(3, 4, 1)	8	(2, 4, 7)
5	(4, 7, 2)	9	(2, 6, 1)
6	(5, 9, 1)	10	(3, 5, 3)

We can confirm that $p - 4 + a + b + cp > abc - 1$ in each case. Thus, the p -tuple

$$\left(\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{p-4}, a, b, \frac{p - 4 + a + b + cp}{abc - 1}, cp \right)$$

is an element of $C_3(p)$. This proves the assertion. □

This theorem provides an affirmative answer to the Shiu’s question.

Question 1 (Shiu [6]). Is Hypothesis $\mathcal{H}_3$ true for all the primes in the arithmetic progression $n \equiv 13 \pmod{88}$?

Next, we obtain another sufficient condition for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.

Theorem 4. For $p \not\equiv 1 \pmod{13}$, it holds that $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. As Theorem 1 and Theorem 3 hold, it suffices to show the case $p \equiv 1 \pmod{13860}$. We seek a triple of positive integers (a, b, c) satisfying either Congruence (3) or Shiu’s Congruence (2). Using direct computation, we find the following table for any prime $p = 180180m + 13860i + 1$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 12$):

$p \pmod{13}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(5, 21, 1)	
3	(12, 12, 1)	
4	(2, 7, 1)	
5		(9, 13, $1540m + 237$)
6	(3, 3, 3)	
7		(7, 13, $1980m + 457$)
8	(10, 4, 1)	
9	(3, 9, 1)	
10		(4, 13, $3465m + 2932$)
11	(7, 7, 4)	
12		(2, 13, $6930m + 6397$)

We can confirm that all triples provides a solution to the equation

$$p(p - 4 + x_{p-3} + x_{p-2} + x_{p-1} + x_p) = x_{p-3}x_{p-2}x_{p-1}x_p$$

with $x_i \geq 2$ ($i = p - 3, p - 2, p - 1, p$).

This proves the theorem. □

Combining Theorem 3 and Theorem 4 with Theorem 1, we deduce the following.

Theorem 5. Let $p \geq 7$ be a prime. If $p \not\equiv 1 \pmod{180180}$, then it holds that $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.

We can obtain similar results for other primes p theoretically. For example, if $p \not\equiv 1, 9 \pmod{19}$ then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$. Additionally, for any prime $q < 110$, we compute which of the positive integers $r < q$ satisfy the condition that if $p \equiv r \pmod{q}$ then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$. We summarize our computation in the supplement table in Appendix.

4. Extension of the Interval with $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$

In this section, we extend Shiu’s result for $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$. Shiu observed that $C_3(n)$ is not empty for $6 \leq n \leq 1260001$; refer to Theorem 1 [6]. In Sections 2 and 3, we presented additional sufficient conditions for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$. To simplify our computation, we demonstrate one more sufficient condition for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.

Theorem 6. *If $p \equiv 96 \pmod{323}$, then $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. For any prime p with $p \equiv 96 \pmod{323}$, we find that $(a, b, c) = (4, 9, 9)$ satisfies Congruence (3). Thus,

$$\left(\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{p-4}, 4, 9, \frac{10p+9}{323}, 9p \right) \in C_3(p).$$

□

Applying the aforementioned sufficient conditions for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$ and the supplement table in Appendix, we find that $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ for any integer $6 \leq n \leq 10^{24}$, except for

$$\text{Ex} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 19129236662455707387601, 70584784284435496475401, \\ 284831454575248704903781, 629104994245323607611601, \\ 777087022848776611171201 \end{array} \right\}.$$

By contrast, we can find an element of $C_3(n)$ for each $n \in \text{Ex}$ as shown in the following table:

n	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)
19129236662455707387601	(8, 43, 2740692129795356747815)
70584784284435496475401	(3, 882263, 5041772210894058262707)
284831454575248704903781	(274, 617, 1684815001805585686)
629104994245323607611601	(4, 197161, 209701930649994689906701)
777087022848776611171201	(8, 837439, 111012448405766099003029)

Therefore, we have extended Shiu’s result for $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ as follows.

Theorem 7. *It holds that $C_3(n) \neq \emptyset$ for $6 \leq n \leq 10^{24}$.*

Acknowledgment. This work was supported by Grant-in-Aid for JSPS Research Fellow (Grant Number: JP19J10705). The author would like to thank the referee, who indicated several mistakes in the previous version of this paper and suggested some helpful comments.

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Appendix

In this appendix, we present a list of sufficient conditions for $C_3(p) \neq \emptyset$ combined with the explicit solutions. As shown in the previous sections, it suffices to find a triple (a, b, c) satisfying either our Congruence (3) or Shiu’s Congruence (2).

For $p = 180180(17m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 16$):

$p \pmod{17}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(4, 13, 1)	(4, 13, $58905m + 38116$)
3	(5, 15, 5)	(3, 17, $60060m + 17665$)
4	(2, 3, 3)	(2, 9, $170170m + 100101$)
5	(2, 9, 1)	(3, 6, $170170m + 40041$)
6	(3, 6, 1)	(9, 17, $20020m + 17665$)
7		(9, 17, $20020m + 725$)
8		
9	(3, 4, 10)	(3, 4, $255255m + 45055$)
10		(4, 17, $45045m + 37096$)
11		
12		(2, 17, $90090m + 10599$)
13	(5, 7, 1)	(5, 17, $36036m + 27557$)
14		(7, 17, $25740m + 10599$)
15	(11, 31, 1)	(3, 17, $60060m + 3533$)
16	(8, 15, 1)	(2, 17, $90090m + 63593$)

For $p = 180180(19m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 18$):

$p \pmod{19}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(3, 15, 11)	(3, 15, $76076m + 52063$)
3	(37, 37, 1)	
4	(11, 15, 3)	(11, 15, $20748m + 1095$)
5		(3, 95, $12012m + 8851$)
6	(4, 10, 10)	(2, 133, $12870m + 5419$)
7	(4, 5, 1)	(13, 19, $13860m + 1459$)
8	(9, 17, 1)	
9		
10	(6, 16, 1)	(10, 19, $18018m + 2845$)
11		(2, 627, $2730m + 2299$)
12	(7, 11, 1)	(7, 11, $44460m + 23401$)
13	(2, 4, 12)	(7, 19, $25740m + 5419$)
14		(2, 19, $90090m + 80607$)
15	(2, 10, 1)	(5, 19, $36036m + 20863$)
16	(3, 11, 15)	(4, 19, $45045m + 1459$)
17	(2, 12, 4)	(3, 19, $60060m + 56899$)
18	(2, 5, 2)	(2, 19, $90090m + 56899$)

For $p = 180180(23m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 22$):

$p \pmod{23}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(4, 13, 4)	(23, 45, $4004m + 1915$)
3	(4, 4, 13)	(7, 69, $8580m + 8207$)
4	(4, 37, 7)	
5	(7, 10, 1)	(7, 10, $59202m + 54055$)
6		
7		
8	(3, 8, 1)	
9	(2, 3, 4)	(2, 3, $690690m + 570574$)
10		
11	(2, 4, 3)	
12	(3, 3, 18)	(12, 23, $15015m + 3917$)
13	(3, 18, 3)	
14	(2, 6, 2)	(2, 6, $345345m + 75077$)
15	(7, 37, 4)	
16		(4, 115, $9009m + 1567$)
17	(5, 81, 5)	
18	(2, 18, 1)	(2, 69, $30030m + 3917$)
19	(5, 5, 81)	(5, 23, $36036m + 21935$)
20	(4, 6, 1)	
21	(4, 7, 37)	(3, 23, $60060m + 33947$)
22	(3, 4, 2)	(2, 23, $90090m + 3917$)

For $p = 180180(29m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 28$):

$p \pmod{29}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(4, 17, 3)	
4	(3, 3, 13)	(3, 3, $580580m + 20033$)
5		
6		
7	(4, 16, 5)	
8	(2, 15, 1)	(2, 15, $174174m + 72073$)
9		(7, 87, $8580m + 6509$)
10	(3, 10, 1)	(3, 39, $44660m + 4621$)
11	(5, 6, 1)	
12		
13		
14	(5, 16, 4)	
15	(7, 25, 1)	(15, 29, $12012m + 9941$)
16		(2, 29, $90090m + 15533$)
17		
18	(3, 5, 2)	(3, 5, $348348m + 300302$)
19		

$p \pmod{29}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
20	(3, 17, 4)	(9, 13, $44660m + 24641$)
21	(3, 5, 3)	(2, 63, $41470m + 37183$)
22		(2, 29, $90090m + 21747$)
23	(19, 55, 1)	(4, 87, $15015m + 8802$)
24	(2, 3, 5)	(2, 29, $90090m + 83877$)
25	(43, 85, 1)	(5, 29, $36036m + 9941$)
26	(3, 13, 3)	(3, 13, $133980m + 83163$)
27	(4, 5, 16)	(3, 29, $60060m + 57989$)
28		(2, 29, $90090m + 27959$)

For $p = 180180(31m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 30$):

$p \pmod{31}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(11, 171, 3)	
3	(61, 61, 1)	(31, 91, $1980m + 511$)
4		
5	(4, 7, 10)	(3, 93, $20020m + 10333$)
6		
7		
8		
9	(4, 4, 2)	
10	(4, 16, 16)	
11	(15, 29, 1)	(21, 31, $8580m + 2491$)
12	(2, 4, 4)	(6, 186, $5005m + 2099$)
13	(16, 16, 4)	
14	(3, 7, 3)	(3, 7, $265980m + 180183$)
15	(7, 7, 19)	
16	(7, 10, 4)	(31, 39, $4620m + 4322$)
17	(6, 16, 1)	(3, 31, $60060m + 3875$)
18	(5, 25, 1)	(5, 93, $12012m + 2325$)
19		(13, 31, $13860m + 4471$)
20		(4, 93, $15015m + 6781$)
21	(3, 21, 1)	(11, 31, $16380m + 9511$)
22	(4, 10, 7)	(10, 31, $18018m + 12787$)
23	(3, 3, 7)	(3, 3, $620620m + 520527$)
24	(2, 16, 1)	(4, 31, $45045m + 43592$)
25	(7, 9, 1)	(7, 31, $25740m + 2491$)
26		(6, 31, $30030m + 6781$)
27	(4, 8, 1)	(5, 31, $36036m + 12787$)
28		(4, 31, $45045m + 21796$)
29	(2, 8, 2)	(3, 31, $60060m + 36811$)
30	(5, 5, 5)	(2, 31, $90090m + 66841$)

For $p = 180180(37m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 36$):

$p \pmod{37}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
0	(7, 34, 7)	
2	(6, 31, 1)	
3	(36, 36, 1)	
4	(13, 205, 1)	
5	(7, 7, 34)	
6	(4, 7, 4)	(4, 7, 238095m + 115834)
7		
8	(19, 19, 4)	
9	(7, 16, 1)	(2, 37, 90090m + 34089)
10	(2, 19, 1)	
11		(3, 37, 60060m + 58437)
12	(22, 106, 1)	
13		
14		
15		
16	(12, 34, 1)	
17	(5, 5, 3)	(7, 37, 25740m + 19479)
18	(4, 4, 7)	
19		
20		
21		(7, 37, 25740m + 24349)
22		(4, 37, 45045m + 10957)
23	(4, 28, 1)	(3, 185, 12012m + 6493)
24	(3, 5, 5)	(2, 37, 90090m + 75481)
25	(3, 25, 1)	(13, 37, 13860m + 1873)
26		
27		
28		(10, 37, 18018m + 487)
29	(5, 15, 1)	
30		(5, 37, 36036m + 22401)
31		(7, 37, 1980m + 1837)
32		(2, 37, 6930m + 5619)
33		(5, 37, 2772m + 1873)
34		(4, 37, 3465m + 1873)
35		(3, 37, 4620m + 1873)
36		(2, 37, 6930m + 1837)

For $p = 13860(41m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 40$):

$p \pmod{41}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(40, 40, 1)	
4		
5	(2, 3, 7)	(2, 3, $1231230m + 1141147$)
6		
7		
8		
9	(2, 7, 3)	(2, 7, $527670m + 450453$)
10		
11	(2, 11, 1)	(2, 21, $175890m + 55771$)
12	(3, 11, 5)	(3, 11, $223860m + 10925$)
13	(3, 4, 24)	(3, 4, $615615m + 480504$)
14	(3, 14, 1)	(3, 14, $175890m + 90091$)
15		(3, 41, $60060m + 14649$)
16	(6, 7, 1)	(6, 7, $175890m + 171601$)
17		(11, 41, $175890m + 171601$)
18		
19		
20	(3, 24, 4)	
21	(8, 36, 1)	(21, 41, $8580m + 5441$)
22		
23	(3, 32, 3)	
24	(5, 33, 1)	(5, 33, $44772m + 37129$)
25		
26		
27	(3, 5, 11)	(3, 5, $492492m + 12023$)
28	(4, 22, 7)	
29		
30	(11, 15, 1)	(4, 7, $263835m + 57937$)
31	(3, 3, 32)	(11, 41, $16380m + 15581$)
32		
33		
34		
35	(4, 24, 3)	
36	(7, 22, 4)	(6, 41, $30030m + 18311$)
37		(5, 11, $134316m + 9831$)
38	(5, 11, 3)	(5, 11, $134316m + 9831$)
39	(3, 7, 2)	(3, 41, $60060m + 48341$)
40	(10, 37, 1)	(2, 41, $90090m + 48341$)

For $p = 13860(43m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 42$):

$p \pmod{43}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
0	(2, 2, 11)	
2		
3	(2, 4, 27)	
4		
5	(3, 67, 3)	(6, 6, $215215m + 45051$)
6		
7		
8	(5, 69, 1)	
9		
10		
11		
12	(10, 13, 1)	(10, 13, $59598m + 19405$)
13		
14	(2, 22, 22)	
15		
16	(2, 9, 12)	(4, 11, $176085m + 94186$)
17	(25, 31, 1)	
18	(14, 40, 1)	
19		
20		
21		
22	(7, 79, 7)	(22, 43, $8190m + 2857$)
23	(7, 37, 1)	(7, 129, $8580m + 5587$)
24	(3, 3, 67)	(3, 3, $860860m + 820887$)
25		
26		
27		
28		
29	(3, 29, 1)	(15, 43, $12012m + 5587$)
30		
31		(13, 43, $13860m + 967$)
32		(6, 43, $30030m + 11174$)
33	(2, 22, 1)	(2, 22, $176085m + 118756$)
34	(4, 27, 2)	(10, 43, $18018m + 17599$)
35	(22, 22, 4)	
36		
37		(7, 43, $25740m + 22747$)
38	(2, 27, 4)	(2, 129, $30030m + 5587$)
39		(4, 43, $45045m + 35617$)
40	(2, 11, 2)	(4, 43, $45045m + 35617$)
41	(16, 121, 1)	(3, 43, $60060m + 5587$)
42	(2, 12, 9)	(2, 43, $90090m + 35617$)

For $p = 180180(47m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 46$):

$p \pmod{47}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(46, 46, 1)	(5, 423, $4004m + 2215$)
4	(6, 17, 6)	
5		
6		
7	(15, 22, 1)	(15, 22, $25662m + 16927$)
8		
9		
10	(6, 6, 17)	(6, 6, $235235m + 115132$)
11	(3, 10, 11)	(3, 10, $282282m + 216227$)
12		
13		
14		
15	(23, 45, 1)	
16	(3, 16, 1)	
17	(3, 3, 21)	(3, 3, $940940m + 400421$)
18	(2, 6, 4)	(2, 6, $705705m + 495499$)
19		
20		
21		(3, 141, $20020m + 10649$)
22	(2, 8, 3)	
23		
24		
25		
26	(2, 3, 8)	(2, 3, $1411410m + 1291298$)
27		(7, 47, $25740m + 4929$)
28	(2, 12, 2)	
29	(3, 8, 2)	(3, 11, $256620m + 191110$)
30		
31	(10, 11, 3)	(10, 11, $76986m + 22935$)
32	(7, 27, 1)	
33		(3, 235, $12012m + 10223$)
34	(9, 21, 1)	
35	(31, 91, 1)	
36	(2, 24, 1)	
37	(3, 4, 4)	(3, 4, $705705m + 675679$)
38		
39		
40	(2, 4, 6)	
41	(4, 12, 1)	
42	(6, 8, 1)	(2, 47, $90090m + 30669$)
43		(5, 47, $36036m + 22235$)
44	(7, 9, 3)	(7, 9, $134420m + 120123$)
45	(4, 6, 2)	(3, 47, $60060m + 10223$)
46	(4, 4, 3)	(2, 47, $90090m + 40253$)

For $p = 180180(53m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 52$):

$p \pmod{53}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(3, 24, 67)	
3	(4, 16, 82)	
4		
5		
6	(7, 91, 1)	
7		
8		
9	(3, 11, 45)	(5, 159, $12012m + 9519$)
10	(5, 85, 1)	
11		
12	(3, 6, 3)	(3, 6, $530530m + 180183$)
13	(2, 7, 19)	(2, 7, $682110m + 128719$)
14	(2, 27, 1)	
15	(3, 9, 2)	
16		(6, 318, $5005m + 3683$)
17	(4, 82, 16)	
18	(3, 18, 1)	
19		
20		
21	(6, 9, 1)	
22	(7, 7, 13)	
23		
24	(13, 49, 1)	
25		
26		
27		
28	(7, 19, 2)	
29		
30	(3, 3, 6)	(3, 3, $1061060m + 660666$)
31	(2, 19, 7)	
32	(4, 31, 3)	
33	(4, 40, 1)	(7, 159, $8580m + 1457$)
34	(17, 25, 1)	
35	(5, 5, 17)	
36		
37	(2, 3, 9)	(2, 3, $1591590m + 900909$)
38	(2, 9, 3)	(2, 9, $530530m + 220223$)
39		(3, 53, $60060m + 15865$)
40	(11, 45, 3)	(14, 53, $12870m + 1457$)
41		(2, 159, $30030m + 28897$)
42	(10, 16, 1)	(4, 159, $15015m + 12182$)
43	(4, 4, 10)	
44	(3, 67, 24)	
45		

$p \pmod{53}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
46		
47	(3, 31, 4)	
48		(2, 159, $30030m + 27197$)
49		(5, 53, $36036m + 27197$)
50	(5, 17, 5)	
51	(4, 10, 4)	(3, 53, $60060m + 27197$)
52		(2, 53, $90090m + 27197$)

For $p = 180180(59m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 58$):

$p \pmod{59}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4		
5	(4, 19, 7)	
6	(25, 85, 1)	
7		
8	(2, 5, 6)	(2, 5, $1063062m + 864870$)
9		
10	(3, 3, 46)	(3, 3, $1181180m + 560606$)
11	(3, 5, 4)	(3, 5, $708708m + 216220$)
12	(3, 93, 11)	
13		
14		
15		(5, 59, $36036m + 22599$)
16	(2, 3, 10)	(2, 3, $1771770m + 810820$)
17		
18	(29, 57, 1)	
19	(2, 6, 5)	(2, 6, $885885m + 840845$)
20	(3, 20, 1)	(3, 20, $177177m + 138139$)
21		
22	(4, 15, 1)	(4, 15, $177177m + 78079$)
23	(5, 12, 1)	(5, 12, $177177m + 48049$)
24	(4, 31, 10)	
25	(5, 26, 5)	(3, 11, $322140m + 300393$)
26	(5, 5, 26)	
27	(4, 37, 2)	
28	(10, 31, 4)	
29	(3, 4, 5)	(3, 4, $885885m + 225230$)
30		
31	(2, 4, 31)	
32	(4, 6, 32)	
33	(3, 46, 3)	
34	(11, 93, 3)	
35	(2, 15, 2)	(2, 15, $354354m + 84086$)

$p \pmod{59}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
36		
37	(5, 6, 2)	$(5, 6, 354354m + 318320)$
38	(4, 7, 19)	$(4, 7, 379665m + 276724)$
39		$(7, 59, 25740m + 14397)$
40		
41		
42		
43	(4, 5, 3)	$(4, 5, 531531m + 468471)$
44		
45	(2, 30, 1)	$(3, 59, 60060m + 32575)$
46	(4, 32, 6)	
47	(16, 24, 2)	
48		
49	(7, 17, 1)	
50		
51		
52	(2, 37, 4)	$(4, 59, 45045m + 16033)$
53	(6, 10, 1)	$(6, 10, 177177m + 33034)$
54	(22, 169, 1)	$(2, 59, 90090m + 1527)$
55	(4, 10, 31)	$(5, 59, 36036m + 30539)$
56	(3, 10, 2)	$(3, 10, 354354m + 240242)$
57	(2, 10, 3)	$(3, 59, 60060m + 30539)$
58		$(2, 59, 90090m + 30539)$

For $p = 180180(61m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 60$):

$p \pmod{61}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	(11, 111, 1)	
3	(2, 9, 17)	$(2, 9, 610610m + 260277)$
4	(6, 51, 1)	
5		
6		
7	(3, 95, 3)	
8		
9	(22, 25, 1)	
10		
11		
12		
13	(9, 17, 2)	
14		
15		

$p \pmod{61}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
16	(2, 31, 1)	
17		(9, 61, $20020m + 8205$)
18		
19		
20	(4, 31, 31)	
21		
22		
23		(10, 61, $18018m + 12406$)
24		
25	(31, 31, 4)	
26		
27	(15, 57, 1)	
28		
29	(2, 17, 9)	
30		
31		
32		(61, 91, $1980m + 1201$)
33	(13, 169, 1)	
34		
35		
36	(5, 49, 1)	
37		
38	(4, 46, 1)	
39	(7, 7, 5)	
40		
41	(3, 41, 1)	(21, 61, $8580m + 4501$)
42	(7, 35, 1)	
43		
44		
45		
46		
47	(3, 3, 95)	(3, 305, $12012m + 9649$)
48		(2, 427, $12870m + 211$)
49		(13, 61, $13860m + 3181$)
50		
51		(11, 61, $16380m + 10741$)
52		(10, 61, $18018m + 15655$)
53		
54		
55		(7, 61, $25740m + 13081$)
56		(6, 61, $30030m + 21661$)
57		(5, 61, $36036m + 33673$)
58		(4, 61, $45045 + 6646$)
59		(3, 61, $60060m + 21661$)
60	(5, 7, 7)	(2, 61, $90090m + 51691$)

For $p = 180180(67m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 66$):

$p \pmod{67}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(66, 66, 1)	
4		
5		
6		
7		
8	(7, 115, 1)	
9		
10		
11		
12		
13	(3, 5, 9)	(3, 5, $804804m + 576585$)
14	(2, 24, 7)	
15	(12, 14, 2)	
16		
17	(16, 21, 1)	
18	(4, 196, 1)	
19		(3, 67, $60060m + 4483$)
20	(5, 5, 59)	
21	(3, 9, 5)	
22		
23	(6, 6, 121)	(6, 6, $335335m + 105226$)
24		
25	(4, 17, 1)	(3, 3, $1341340m + 580595$)
26	(22, 64, 1)	
27	(25, 193, 1)	
28	(2, 4, 42)	
29		
30	(3, 15, 3)	(2, 14, $431145m + 315327$)
31	(5, 9, 3)	(5, 9, $268268m + 212215$)
32	(4, 12, 7)	
33	(11, 61, 1)	
34		
35		
36		
37		
38	(6, 56, 1)	
39		
40	(2, 7, 24)	(2, 7, $862290m + 283164$)
41		(3, 67, $60060m + 23307$)
42		
43		
44	(2, 12, 14)	(7, 67, $25740m + 14599$)
45	(3, 45, 1)	

$p \pmod{67}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
46		
47	(13, 31, 1)	(7, 67, 25740m + 19209)
48		
49		
50		
51	(2, 34, 1)	(4, 7, 431145m + 424722)
52		(4, 67, 45045m + 2017)
53	(5, 27, 1)	(3, 67, 60060m + 6275)
54		
55		(13, 67, 13860m + 3103)
56		(12, 67, 15015m + 4258)
57	(9, 15, 1)	
58	(7, 24, 2)	(10, 67, 18018m + 7261)
59	(2, 42, 4)	(2, 42, 143715m + 66499)
60		
61		(7, 67, 25740m + 14983)
62	(2, 17, 2)	(2, 67, 90090m + 57819)
63	(19, 127, 1)	(5, 67, 36036m + 25279)
64	(7, 12, 4)	(4, 67, 45045m + 34288)
65		(3, 67, 60060m + 49303)
66		(2, 67, 90090m + 79333)

For $p = 180180(71m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 70$):

$p \pmod{71}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(141, 141, 1)	
4		
5	(4, 16, 10)	
6		(6, 71, 30030m + 21571)
7	(3, 11, 28)	(3, 11, 387660m + 256648)
8		
9	(23, 34, 1)	(11, 28, 41535m + 22818)
10		
11		
12		
13	(2, 11, 42)	(2, 11, 581490m + 188412)
14	(2, 4, 9)	(3, 5, 852852m + 228247)
15		
16	(3, 8, 3)	
17		
18		
19		
20	(3, 12, 2)	(3, 12, 355355m + 330332)

$p \pmod{71}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
21	(6, 6, 2)	(6, 6, $355355m + 310312$)
22		
23		
24	(3, 24, 1)	
25		
26		
27	(2, 9, 4)	(5, 71, $36036m + 19287$)
28	(3, 17, 39)	
29	(8, 9, 1)	
30	(3, 4, 6)	(3, 4, $1066065m + 390396$)
31	(11, 42, 2)	(11, 42, $27690m + 8582$)
32		
33	(2, 12, 3)	(2, 154, $41535m + 8193$)
34	(4, 6, 3)	
35		
36	(10, 64, 1)	(36, 71, $5005m + 141$)
37	(4, 10, 16)	(6, 21, $101530m + 98701$)
38	(4, 4, 40)	
39	(7, 61, 1)	
40	(2, 6, 6)	(2, 6, $1066065m + 855861$)
41		
42	(2, 18, 2)	(2, 18, $355355m + 245247$)
43		
44	(2, 42, 11)	(2, 42, $152295m + 87956$)
45	(16, 40, 1)	
46		
47	(7, 7, 29)	
48		
49		
50	(5, 125, 5)	
51	(3, 28, 11)	(21, 71, $8580m + 1571$)
52		
53		
54	(2, 36, 1)	
55	(3, 3, 8)	(3, 3, $1421420m + 1361368$)
56	(15, 19, 1)	
57		(15, 71, $12012m + 10151$)
58	(17, 39, 3)	(2, 497, $12870m + 10151$)
59		
60	(2, 3, 12)	(4, 71, $45045m + 30453$)

$p \pmod{71}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
61	(11, 13, 1)	(3, 39, $109340m + 67777$)
62	(4, 18, 1)	
63	(4, 40, 4)	
64	(6, 12, 1)	
65		
66	(5, 19, 3)	(6, 71, $30030m + 10151$)
67	(7, 29, 7)	(5, 71, $36036m + 10151$)
68	(4, 9, 2)	(4, 9, $355355m + 80082$)
69		(3, 71, $60060m + 10151$)
70	(3, 6, 4)	(2, 71, $90090m + 10151$)

For $p = 180180(73m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 72$):

$p \pmod{73}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4		
5	(6, 61, 1)	
6		
7		
8		(2, 219, $30030m + 2057$)
9	(4, 55, 1)	(4, 55, $59787m + 30304$)
10		(4, 73, $45045m + 42577$)
11		
12		
13		
14	(5, 117, 1)	
15		
16		
17		
18		
19	(2, 37, 1)	
20		
21		
22		
23	(8, 8, 8)	
24		
25		
26		
27	(11, 31, 3)	
28		
29		
30	(5, 257, 5)	

$p \pmod{73}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
31	(9, 21, 17)	
32		
33		
34	(7, 7, 3)	
35		
36	(4, 115, 10)	
37		
38	(9, 65, 1)	
39	(8, 64, 1)	
40		
41	(5, 9, 13)	
42		
43	(31, 106, 1)	
44		
45		
46	(13, 45, 1)	
47		(3, 219, $20020m + 3291$)
48		
49	(3, 49, 1)	
50		
51		
52		
53		
54	(3, 7, 7)	(3, 7, $626340m + 145867$)
55	(17, 21, 9)	
56	(5, 5, 257)	(7, 949, $1980m + 217$)
57	(5, 13, 9)	
58	(36, 71, 1)	
59	(10, 22, 1)	(3, 73, $60060m + 25505$)
60		
61	(7, 21, 1)	(13, 73, $13860m + 4177$)
62		
63	(29, 141, 1)	
64		(10, 73, $18018m + 11107$)
65		
66		(4, 73, $45045m + 22214$)
67		(7, 73, $25740m + 23977$)
68	(10, 10, 46)	(2, 219, $30030m + 11107$)
69		(5, 73, $36036m + 29125$)
70	(9, 13, 5)	(4, 73, $45045m + 11107$)
71		(3, 73, $60060m + 41137$)
72	(12, 67, 1)	(2, 73, $90090m + 11107$)

For $p = 180180(79m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 78$):

$p \pmod{79}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(78, 78, 1)	
4		
5		
6		
7	(2, 4, 10)	
8		
9	(3, 123, 3)	
10	(2, 9, 22)	(2, 9, $790790m + 120142$)
11		
12		
13		
14	(3, 3, 123)	(3, 3, $1581580m + 1401523$)
15		
16		
17		
18	(11, 36, 1)	(11, 36, $35945m + 22296$)
19		
20		
21	(7, 34, 1)	
22		
23	(4, 10, 2)	
24		
25		
26	(2, 5, 8)	(2, 5, $1423422m + 126134$)
27		
28		
29		
30	(2, 10, 4)	(2, 10, $711711m + 585589$)
31	(5, 16, 1)	
32	(6, 11, 6)	(6, 11, $215670m + 40956$)
33		
34		
35	(22, 202, 4)	(9, 395, $4004m + 963$)
36		
37		
38	(13, 73, 1)	
39		

$p \pmod{79}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
40	(31, 51, 1)	
41		
42		
43		
44		
45	(6, 66, 1)	(6, 66, $35945m + 2731$)
46		
47		
48		
49		
50		
51	(2, 24, 107)	
52	(4, 4, 5)	(6, 6, $395395m + 340351$)
53	(3, 53, 1)	
54		
55		
56		
57		
58		
59	(19, 25, 1)	(7, 79, $25740m + 16617$)
60	(2, 40, 1)	
61		
62		
63	(24, 107, 2)	
64		
65	(43, 463, 1)	(3, 395, $12012m + 8971$)
66		(14, 79, $12870m + 5539$)
67		(13, 79, $13860m + 1579$)
68		(7, 79, $25740m + 20527$)
69	(4, 20, 1)	
70	(9, 22, 2)	(10, 79, $18018m + 2965$)
71		
72	(8, 10, 1)	
73	(2, 20, 2)	(7, 79, $25740m + 5539$)
74		(2, 79, $90090m + 80967$)
75		(5, 79, $36036m + 20983$)
76	(5, 8, 2)	(4, 79, $45045m + 11974$)
77	(2, 22, 9)	(3, 79, $60060m + 57019$)
78	(2, 8, 5)	(2, 79, $90090m + 57019$)

For $p = 180180(83m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 82$):

$p \pmod{83}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4	(11, 151, 1)	
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10	(3, 4, 7)	(3, 4, $1246245m + 660667$)
11	(2, 3, 14)	(2, 3, $2492490m + 360374$)
12	(15, 24, 3)	
13		
14		
15		
16	(5, 133, 1)	
17		
18	(3, 31, 25)	
19	(4, 7, 3)	(4, 7, $534105m + 32178$)
20	(3, 25, 31)	
21	(13, 115, 1)	
22		
23	(2, 7, 6)	(2, 7, $1068210m + 553416$)
24	(41, 81, 1)	
25		
26	(10, 25, 1)	(3, 15, $332332m + 120144$)
27		
28	(3, 28, 1)	(3, 28, $178035m + 105106$)
29		
30	(49, 61, 1)	
31	(4, 21, 1)	(4, 21, $178035m + 77221$)
32	(3, 7, 4)	(3, 7, $712140m + 34324$)
33		
34	(7, 12, 1)	(7, 12, $178035m + 49336$)
35		
36		
37		
38	(4, 52, 2)	
39		(9, 83, $20020m + 6995$)
40	(7, 7, 61)	

$p \pmod{83}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
41	(2, 6, 7)	(2, 6, $1246245m + 720727$)
42		
43		
44		
45		
46		
47		
48	(3, 3, 37)	(3, 3, $1661660m + 1461497$)
49	(2, 21, 2)	(2, 21, $356070m + 175892$)
50		
51	(3, 14, 2)	(3, 14, $356070m + 257402$)
52		
53		
54	(4, 6, 45)	
55		
56		
57	(22, 34, 1)	(3, 249, $20020m + 8201$)
58		
59		
60		
61		
62	(9, 37, 1)	
63	(2, 42, 1)	(2, 42, $178035m + 17161$)
64	(16, 26, 1)	(6, 6, $415415m + 295325$)
65		
66	(3, 24, 15)	
67		
68		
69		
70	(25, 31, 3)	
71		
72	(2, 4, 52)	
73	(2, 52, 4)	
74	(3, 37, 3)	
75	(6, 14, 1)	(6, 14, $178035m + 83656$)
76		
77		
78		(2, 249, $30030m + 9407$)
79		(5, 83, $36036m + 33431$)
80	(2, 14, 3)	(2, 14, $534105m + 289578$)
81		(3, 83, $60060m + 9407$)
82		(2, 83, $90090m + 69467$)

For $p = 180180(89m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 88$):

$p \pmod{89}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8	(7, 7, 109)	
9		
10		
11	(4, 67, 1)	
12		
13		
14	(3, 6, 5)	(3, 6, $890890m + 630635$)
15		
16	(3, 3, 10)	(3, 3, $1781780m + 1181190$)
17		
18		
19	(2, 15, 3)	(2, 15, $534534m + 318321$)
20	(3, 10, 3)	(3, 10, $534534m + 306309$)
21		
22		
23	(2, 45, 1)	(2, 45, $178178m + 90091$)
24		(2, 89, $90090m + 43527$)
25	(3, 15, 2)	(3, 15, $356356m + 164166$)
26		
27		
28		
29	(9, 17, 32)	
30	(3, 30, 1)	(3, 30, $178178m + 62063$)
31	(12, 34, 12)	
32		
33		
34		
35	(5, 18, 1)	(5, 18, $178178m + 42043$)
36	(6, 15, 1)	(6, 15, $178178m + 38039$)
37	(9, 10, 1)	(9, 10, $178178m + 34035$)
38		
39		
40	(17, 32, 9)	
41		
42		
43		
44		
45	(11, 81, 1)	(45, 89, $4004m + 45$)

$p \pmod{89}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
46		
47		
48	(8, 78, 1)	
49		
50	(2, 3, 15)	$(2, 3, 2672670m + 2402415)$
51		
52	(3, 4, 52)	$(3, 4, 1336335m + 1141192)$
53		
54	(45, 45, 4)	
55	(29, 43, 1)	
56	(5, 9, 2)	$(5, 9, 356356m + 272274)$
57		
58		
59	(3, 7, 17)	$(3, 7, 763620m + 531977)$
60		
61	(3, 52, 4)	$(3, 52, 102795m + 66994)$
62	(2, 5, 9)	$(2, 5, 1603602m + 1009017)$
63	(3, 5, 6)	$(3, 89, 60060m + 36441)$
64		
65	(5, 6, 3)	$(5, 6, 534534m + 300303)$
66	(4, 49, 5)	
67		
68		
69		$(7, 89, 25740m + 12147)$
70	(133, 265, 1)	
71		
72	(11, 21, 1)	
73	(2, 9, 5)	$(2, 9, 890890m + 340345)$
74		
75	(7, 109, 7)	$(3, 445, 12012m + 4049)$
76	(4, 52, 3)	$(2, 89, 90090m + 28343)$
77		
78		$(12, 89, 15015m + 4049)$
79	(5, 49, 4)	$(4, 445, 9009m + 2227)$
80	(4, 5, 49)	$(4, 5, 801801m + 180229)$
81		
82	(22, 85, 1)	
83		
84	(7, 17, 3)	$(2, 89, 90090m + 12147)$
85		$(5, 89, 36036m + 4049)$
86		
87	(3, 17, 7)	$(3, 89, 60060m + 4049)$
88		$(2, 89, 90090m + 4049)$

For $p = 180180(97m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 96$):

$p \pmod{97}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4	(8, 85, 1)	
5		
6		
7	(6, 81, 1)	(7, 97, 25740m + 21229)
8		
9		
10	(11, 353, 3)	
11	(3, 151, 3)	
12	(4, 73, 1)	
13		
14		
15		
16		
17		
18	(19, 46, 1)	
19		
20	(4, 7, 52)	(4, 7, 624195m + 173797)
21	(4, 10, 17)	
22		
23		
24	(2, 9, 27)	(2, 9, 970970m + 480507)
25	(2, 49, 1)	
26		
27		
28		
29	(7, 7, 2)	
30		
31		
32	(4, 49, 49)	
33		
34		
35		
36		
37	(3, 3, 151)	(3, 3, 1941940m + 1841991)
38		
39		
40	(7, 14, 1)	

$p \pmod{97}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
41		
42	(4, 52, 7)	
43	(27, 247, 4)	
44		
45	(5, 13, 3)	(5, 13, $268884m + 102567$)
46	(2, 27, 9)	
47		
48		
49		
50		
51		(6, 97, $30030m + 6192$)
52		
53		(5, 291, $12012m + 9783$)
54	(9, 27, 2)	
55		
56		
57		
58		(4, 97, $45045m + 37615$)
59		
60	(2, 7, 7)	(2, 7, $1248390m + 553417$)
61		
62		
63		
64		
65	(3, 65, 1)	(3, 65, $89628m + 41581$)
66		
67		
68		
69	(3, 5, 13)	(3, 5, $1165164m + 792805$)
70	(21, 37, 1)	
71		
72		
73	(10, 17, 4)	
74		
75		
76		
77	(5, 39, 1)	(7, 97, $25740m + 2919$)
78		
79		
80		

$p \pmod{97}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
81		
82		$(4, 97, 45045m + 6037)$
83		
84		$(2, 679, 12870m + 9553)$
85	$(13, 15, 1)$	$(13, 97, 13860m + 7573)$
86	$(7, 52, 4)$	$(4, 291, 15015m + 5263)$
87		
88		$(10, 97, 18018m + 17275)$
89		
90		
91		$(7, 97, 25740m + 9553)$
92		$(2, 97, 90090m + 15789)$
93	$(3, 11, 535)$	$(5, 97, 36036m + 35293)$
94	$(16, 91, 1)$	$(4, 97, 45045m + 35293)$
95	$(3, 13, 5)$	$(3, 97, 60060m + 35293)$
96		$(2, 97, 90090m + 35293)$

For $p = 180180(101m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 100$):

$p \pmod{101}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2	$(10, 91, 1)$	$(10, 91, 19998m + 4951)$
3	$(100, 100, 1)$	
4		
5	$(3, 4, 59)$	$(3, 4, 1516515m + 1501559)$
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11	$(13, 70, 1)$	$(13, 70, 19998m + 9505)$
12		
13		
14		
15		
16		
17		
18		
19		
20	$(4, 4, 19)$	

$p \pmod{101}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
21		
22		
23		
24	(11, 46, 1)	
25		
26	(2, 51, 1)	
27		
28	(2, 3, 17)	(2, 3, 3033030m + 2072087)
29		
30		
31		
32		
33		
34	(3, 34, 1)	
35	(16, 19, 1)	
36		(6, 1111, 2730m + 1811)
37		
38		
39	(3, 15, 9)	(3, 15, 404404m + 164173)
40		
41	(6, 17, 1)	
42	(25, 97, 1)	
43		
44		
45		
46		
47		
48		
49	(3, 59, 4)	
50	(3, 9, 15)	
51		
52		
53		
54		
55		
56		
57		(9, 505, 4004m + 3449)
58	(43, 148, 1)	
59		
60	(5, 81, 1)	

$p \pmod{101}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
61	(4, 59, 3)	
62	(3, 17, 2)	
63	(4, 76, 1)	
64	(7, 10, 13)	(7, 10, 259974m + 154453)
65	(9, 9, 5)	
66		
67		
68		
69		
70		
71	(67, 199, 1)	
72	(2, 17, 3)	(3, 5, 1213212m + 696723)
73		
74	(4, 17, 52)	
75		
76	(9, 45, 1)	
77	(4, 19, 4)	
78		
79	(3, 3, 45)	(3, 3, 2022020m + 620665)
80		
81		(21, 101, 8580m + 6881)
82	(15, 27, 1)	
83		
84		
85	(7, 29, 1)	(7, 130, 19998m + 15841)
86	(10, 13, 7)	(10, 13, 139986m + 5551)
87		(3, 101, 60060m + 17245)
88	(17, 52, 4)	
89		
90	(3, 45, 3)	
91		(11, 101, 16380m + 4541)
92		
93		
94	(5, 27, 3)	(4, 101, 45045m + 892)
95		
96	(9, 15, 3)	(6, 101, 30030m + 15461)
97		(5, 101, 36036m + 27473)
98		
99		(3, 101, 60060m + 45491)
100	(5, 9, 9)	(2, 101, 90090m + 45491)

For $p = 180180(103m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 102$):

$p \pmod{103}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8	(6, 21, 9)	(6, 21, $147290m + 102969$)
9	(4, 58, 4)	
10		
11	(9, 21, 6)	
12		
13		(7, $1339, 1980m + 1807$)
14		
15		
16		
17		
18	(5, 5, 33)	
19		
20	(5, 165, 1)	
21		
22		
23		
24		
25		
26		
27		
28		
29		
30	(4, 13, 2)	(4, 13, $356895m + 13862$)
31		
32	(6, 186, 6)	
33	(10, 31, 1)	
34	(4, 52, 52)	
35		
36		
37		
38	(34, 100, 1)	
39	(2, 13, 4)	(2, 13, $713790m + 159394$)
40		

$p \pmod{103}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
41		
42		
43	(8, 13, 1)	
44	(2, 4, 13)	
45		
46	(3, 23, 3)	
47		
48		
49		
50		
51	(6, 9, 21)	
52		
53		
54		
55	(37, 49, 5)	
56		
57		
58		
59	(6, 86, 1)	(5, 103, $36036m + 2799$)
60	(3, 3, 23)	(3, 3, $2062060m + 660683$)
61		
62		
63	(5, 33, 5)	
64		
65		
66		
67		
68	(16, 58, 1)	(4, 927, $5005m + 1312$)
69	(3, 69, 1)	
70		
71		
72	(7, 59, 1)	
73		
74		
75	(4, 4, 58)	
76	(25, 33, 1)	
77		
78	(2, 52, 1)	
79		
80	(5, 49, 37)	

$p \pmod{103}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
81		
82		
83	(52, 52, 4)	(7, 309, $8580m + 7747$)
84		
85		
86		
87		
88	(61, 76, 1)	
89	(9, 23, 1)	(3, 515, $12012m + 4315$)
90	(4, 26, 1)	
91		(13, 103, $13860m + 11707$)
92		
93		
94	(5, 37, 49)	(10, 103, $18018m + 1032$)
95	(2, 26, 95)	(2, 26, $356895m + 291062$)
96		
97		(7, 103, $25740m + 7747$)
98	(6, 6, 186)	(6, 6, $515515m + 280466$)
99		(5, 103, $36036m + 28339$)
100		(4, 103, $45045m + 1312$)
101	(22, 295, 1)	(3, 103, $60060m + 16327$)
102		(2, 103, $90090m + 46357$)

For $p = 180180(107m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 106$):

$p \pmod{107}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3	(106, 106, 1)	
4	(16, 301, 1)	
5		
6		
7	(4, 58, 6)	(4, 7, $688545m + 424882$)
8	(4, 7, 172)	
9		
10		
11		
12	(3, 10, 25)	(3, 10, $642642m + 72097$)
13		
14		
15		
16		
17		
18	(5, 5, 33)	
19	(10, 25, 3)	
20		

$p \pmod{107}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
21	(2, 6, 9)	(2, 6, $1606605m + 765774$)
22	(2, 4, 67)	
23	(15, 50, 1)	(3, 12, $535535m + 320323$)
24	(3, 12, 3)	
25		
26		
27	(3, 25, 10)	
28		
29	(7, 46, 1)	
30	(3, 18, 2)	
31		
32	(6, 9, 2)	
33		
34		
35	(7, 9, 17)	(7, 9, $306020m + 217377$)
36	(3, 36, 1)	(3, 143, $44940m + 3781$)
37	(2, 97, 37)	
38		
39		
40	(4, 27, 1)	
41	(3, 3, 12)	(3, 3, $2142140m + 2042052$)
42		(2, 107, $90090m + 29469$)
43		
44		
45	(2, 3, 18)	(2, 3, $3213210m + 1441458$)
46	(2, 29, 24)	
47		
48		
49	(4, 67, 2)	
50		
51		
52		
53		
54		
55	(24, 29, 2)	
56		
57		
58		
59		
60		
61		
62		
63	(2, 27, 2)	
64		
65		

$p \pmod{107}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
66		
67	(4, 6, 58)	
68		
69		
70		
71		
72	(7, 172, 4)	
73	(21, 51, 1)	
74		
75	(71, 211, 1)	
76		
77		
78	(4, 9, 3)	(4, 9, $535535m + 420423$)
79		
80		
81	(2, 54, 1)	
82		
83		
84	(3, 9, 4)	(11, 39, $44940m + 1261$)
85	(5, 43, 1)	
86	(13, 33, 1)	(13, 33, $44940m + 34861$)
87		(7, 107, $25740m + 3849$)
88		
89		
90		
91	(3, 6, 6)	(3, 6, $1071070m + 690696$)
92	(2, 24, 29)	
93	(40, 313, 1)	(3, 535, $12012m + 4715$)
94	(2, 67, 4)	(2, 107, $90090m + 69041$)
95	(6, 58, 4)	
96	(3, 4, 9)	(3, 4, $1606605m + 825834$)
97	(6, 18, 1)	
98		
99		
100		
101	(2, 37, 94)	
102	(11, 13, 3)	(2, 107, $90090m + 68199$)
103	(2, 18, 3)	(5, 107, $36036m + 4715$)
104		
105	(6, 6, 3)	(3, 107, $60060m + 52763$)
106	(2, 9, 6)	(2, 107, $90090m + 22733$)

For $p = 180180(109m + i) + 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, 108$):

$p \pmod{109}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8	(6, 91, 1)	(6, 91, $35970m + 24751$)
9	(2, 39, 7)	(2, 39, $251790m + 90097$)
10	(5, 48, 5)	(3, 15, $436436m + 12075$)
11	(5, 5, 48)	
12		
13		
14	(7, 187, 1)	
15	(6, 10, 20)	(6, 10, $327327m + 123143$)
16	(4, 5, 60)	(4, 5, $981981m + 45105$)
17		
18		
19		(7, 109, $25740m + 1417$)
20	(25, 157, 1)	
21		
22		
23		
24		
25		
26		
27	(2, 5, 11)	(2, 5, $1963962m + 810821$)
28	(2, 55, 1)	(2, 55, $178542m + 14743$)
29	(13, 151, 1)	
30		
31		
32		
33	(5, 16, 15)	(21, 26, $35970m + 15511$)
34		
35		
36	(15, 63, 3)	
37	(3, 63, 15)	
38		
39		
40	(36, 106, 1)	

$p \pmod{109}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
41		
42		
43	(5, 22, 1)	(5, 22, $178542m + 22933$)
44		(2, 1199, $8190m + 6537$)
45	(27, 105, 1)	
46	(10, 11, 1)	(10, 11, $178542m + 24571$)
47		
48		
49		
50	(15, 16, 5)	
51		
52		
53	(2, 11, 5)	(2, 11, $892710m + 737105$)
54	(43, 71, 1)	
55	(12, 100, 1)	
56		
57		
58	(9, 97, 1)	
59		
60		
61		
62		
63		
64		
65		(9, 109, $20020m + 17265$)
66		
67		
68	(4, 82, 1)	(2, 7, $1402830m + 1222689$)
69		
70		
71		
72		
73	(3, 73, 1)	
74		
75	(5, 60, 4)	
76	(5, 15, 16)	
77		
78		
79		
80		

$p \pmod{109}$	(a, b, c) satisfying (3)	(a, b, c) satisfying (2)
81		
82		
83		$(3, 327, 20020m + 18367)$
84		
85		
86		
87		
88		
89		$(7, 109, 25740m + 24087)$
90	$(19, 23, 1)$	
91		
92		
93		
94		
95	$(7, 39, 2)$	$(7, 39, 71940m + 68642)$
96		
97		$(13, 109, 13860m + 4069)$
98		$(6, 109, 30030m + 28928)$
99	$(4, 60, 5)$	
100		$(10, 109, 18018m + 5455)$
101		
102		
103		$(7, 109, 25740m + 8029)$
104		$(2, 109, 90090m + 88437)$
105	$(5, 11, 2)$	$(5, 109, 36036m + 23473)$
106		$(4, 109, 45045m + 14464)$
107	$(6, 20, 10)$	$(3, 109, 60060m + 59509)$
108		$(2, 109, 90090m + 59509)$